

Emotional intelligence in teaching: a key to performance and institutional climate in basic education

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the lack of understanding regarding the relationship between emotional intelligence (EI), teaching performance, and institutional climate (IC) in basic education. As a solution, the study proposes evaluating and strengthening teachers' EI to enhance both their performance and the school environment. Using a quantitative, non-experimental, correlational design, the research analyzed a randomly selected sample of 145 teachers. Validated questionnaires measured dimensions such as self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills, as well as teaching preparation and IC. The results reveal significant positive correlations between EI and IC ($r=0.85$) and between teaching performance and IC ($r=0.78$). This suggests that higher EI not only improves teaching effectiveness but also fosters a positive institutional environment. The study concludes that enhancing teachers' EI can optimize both their performance and institutional dynamics, contributing to higher-quality education. The findings support the implementation of EI training programs as a key strategy to improve teaching performance and the school climate (SC).

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1. INTRODUCTION

The problem addressed by this research is the lack of understanding about the relationship between emotional intelligence (EI), classroom teaching performance, and institutional climate (IC) in the context of secondary education. This issue is relevant because these variables are fundamental to ensuring an effective and healthy educational environment, yet their interconnection has not been sufficiently studied or addressed. Furthermore, the study seeks to provide practical solutions by proposing an EI intervention program that could improve both teaching performance and IC.

This research examines the relationship between EI, teaching performance, and IC in basic education. It proposes that higher EI in teachers enhances their performance and contributes to a positive IC. The study explores the extent of this relationship and identifies strategies to strengthen EI in the educational context. Key questions focus on the connection between EI and teaching performance, its influence on IC, and the best ways to develop these competencies in teachers. The main hypothesis asserts that EI has a positive and significant impact on both teaching performance and school climate (SC).

EI is the ability to perceive, understand, control, and evaluate one's own emotions and those of others. According to Filice and Weese [1], it involves monitoring feelings, distinguishing among them,

and using this information to guide thoughts and actions. Additionally, EI is linked to productive social relationships, effective interpersonal behaviors, and general social competencies [2]. Teaching performance refers to teachers' actions and competencies in planning, implementing, and evaluating the teaching-learning process. It includes the ability to motivate students, manage the classroom, and adapt teaching methodologies to achieve positive educational outcomes, which are influenced by factors such as EI and IC [3]. IC is the overall perception of the work environment by teachers and other members of the educational organization. A positive climate is characterized by effective communication, trust, collaboration, and motivation, which foster commitment, job satisfaction, and organizational performance [4].

In recent decades, EI has emerged as a fundamental concept in the educational field, emphasizing its impact on the development of teaching competencies and the improvement of workplace interactions within educational institutions. Filice and Weese [1] defined EI as the ability to perceive, understand, and manage one's own and others' emotions, highlighting its relevance in social and professional contexts. Recent studies have demonstrated that EI contributes to teachers' physical and mental well-being, promotes their professional success, and improves student outcomes [5], [6]. In this context, teaching performance is considered a key indicator of educational quality, encompassing pedagogical skills, the ability to motivate students, and effective classroom management [7]. Research has linked high levels of EI with better teaching performance due to teachers' ability to manage emotions, resolve conflicts, and foster positive learning environments [8]. On the other hand, IC refers to the perception of the work environment and its influence on commitment, satisfaction, and collaboration among organizational members [9]. A favorable IC is associated with trust, effective communication, and organizational support, which facilitate teachers' interactions and optimal performance [10].

The relationship between EI, teaching performance, and IC has been the subject of various studies [11]. High levels of EI have been found to not only directly influence teachers' performance but also foster a positive organizational climate, promoting effectiveness and innovation within educational institutions [12]. This article explores the background and connections among these variables, emphasizing their relevance for improving educational quality and teacher well-being. To support the research, study by Brasseur *et al.* [13] were considered, which developed and validated the profile of emotional competence (PEC), an instrument designed to specifically and separately measure the five basic emotional competencies (identification, understanding, expression, regulation, and use of emotions) at both intrapersonal and interpersonal levels, overcoming the limitations of previous measures. The methodology included four stages: item generation, reduction through psychometric analysis, evaluation of psychometric properties in a representative sample of 5,676 subjects, and external validation through additional studies. The results showed high internal consistency, solid factorial structure, and good concurrent and predictive validity, with significant correlations with variables such as happiness, social relationships, and work performance. It was concluded that the PEC is a reliable and accurate tool for evaluating emotional competencies, useful in educational and research contexts. For this research, the PEC represents an ideal methodological basis for measuring teachers' EI, allowing for a more rigorous and precise analysis of its impact on professional performance and IC.

Additionally, study by Amin *et al.* [14] aimed to analyze the relationship between teachers' EI in higher education institutions in Haryana, India, considering gender and type of institution (government, private, and government-funded). A quantitative methodology with an exploratory-descriptive design was employed, evaluating 400 teachers through an EI inventory and performing statistical analyses such as t-tests and analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results showed that female teachers achieved higher levels of EI compared to male teachers, while no significant differences were found based on the type of institution. The research concluded that gender influences EI levels, highlighting its relevance for teacher training and performance, whereas the type of institution is not a determining factor. This study contributes to our research by validating the influence of gender on EI and emphasizing the need for universal training strategies to improve this competence, optimizing teaching performance and IC.

In the same context, the study by Akhtar and Mali [15] aimed to analyze the relationship between spiritual intelligence and teachers' work engagement in the Jammu district, considering gender differences, place of origin (rural or urban), and levels of work engagement. A quantitative methodology was used, employing surveys and standardized tests to evaluate spiritual intelligence and work engagement, along with statistical techniques such as measures of central tendency, dispersion, t-tests, and correlations. The results revealed a moderate positive relationship between spiritual intelligence and work engagement, significant differences in spiritual intelligence based on gender and place of origin, and between teachers with high and low levels of work engagement. The research concluded that spiritual intelligence influences teachers' performance and work well-being. This study contributes to our research by highlighting how emotional and spiritual aspects impact teaching performance and IC, reinforcing the importance of socio-emotional competencies for improving the educational environment.

On the other hand, study by Kumar and Anshika [16] compared the EI of secondary-level students from two groups: reserved and non-reserved, analyzing how socioeconomic and cultural factors influence

their emotional development. The methodology employed was quantitative, using standardized questionnaires to collect data from 200 students, evenly distributed between both groups. The results showed no significant differences in EI levels between reserved and non-reserved students. The conclusion highlights that, although there are no marked differences, EI plays a crucial role in students' personal and academic development, suggesting the importance of implementing inclusive educational policies and programs that enhance these competencies. This study reinforces the idea that EI is not significantly determined by external factors, emphasizing the possibility of developing it in any context. Moreover, it underscores the relevance of designing interventions and educational policies aimed at improving emotional skills, an approach that aligns with my objective of studying the relationship between EI, teaching performance, and IC.

Similarly, research by Al Shehhi *et al.* [17] aimed to explore the relationship between school principals' levels of EI and the SC as perceived by teachers, also identifying the impact of work experience on principals' EI levels. A quantitative correlational design was used, collecting data from 20 school principals and 200 teachers through the Mayer–Salovey–Caruso emotional intelligence test (MSCEIT) instrument to measure EI and the revised school-level environment questionnaire (R-SLEQ) to evaluate SC. The results showed that most principals had low levels of EI, which negatively affected the SC and the effectiveness of their leadership. The findings highlight the need to integrate EI evaluations into the selection and training processes of school principals, as well as to implement professional development programs focused on emotional skills to improve their performance and the school environment. This study reinforces the importance of EI as a key factor for educational leadership and organizational climate, providing relevant evidence that supports the need to develop EI in educational contexts, aligning with the objective of exploring its relationship with teaching performance and IC. In this same context, the study by Iram [18] highlights the significant impact of teachers' EI on SC, showing how its components influence various aspects of the institutional environment. Conducted with 120 female public school teachers in Lahore using validated instruments and regression analyses, the study concludes that emotionally intelligent teachers contribute positively to the SC. It also emphasizes the importance of integrating emotional skills into teaching strategies and provides guidance for educational leaders on fostering EI to enhance institutional dynamics.

The study by Go *et al.* [19] emphasizes the role of EI and problem compartmentalization as key factors in sustaining effective teaching performance despite personal challenges. Conducted with 160 Filipino public school teachers, the research found a significant positive correlation between EI, the ability to separate personal issues from professional duties, and overall teaching effectiveness. The findings support the integration of emotional regulation and compartmentalization strategies into teacher training programs to enhance well-being and professional performance.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study used a quantitative research approach to examine variables in a structured and measurable way. The design was non-experimental and correlational, focusing on identifying relationships rather than manipulating variables. Specifically, it aimed to explore the association between EI, teaching performance, and IC in basic education teachers.

2.2. Population and sample

The population was composed of 500 teachers from multiple public educational institutions in the Arequipa region. A representative sample of 145 teachers was selected to participate in the study. The selection was carried out through simple random sampling, ensuring fairness and the absence of selection bias.

2.3. Variables studied

This study examines the relationship between EI, teaching performance, and IC within the educational setting. EI is analyzed through key dimensions such as self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Teaching performance is evaluated based on pedagogical competencies, while IC is assessed through factors like communication, trust, motivation, and participation.

2.4. Data collection instruments

To measure the variable of EI, a structured questionnaire adapted from the Bar-On emotional quotient inventory (EQ-i) method developed by Boybanting and Tantiado [20] was used. The questionnaire consists of 50 items organized by dimensions and subdimensions of EI. Responses are scored using a Likert-type scale, as detailed in Table 1.

The questionnaire used to assess teachers' perception of the IC was an adaptation of the instrument developed by Bris [21], incorporating the dimensions of communication, motivation, trust, and participation.

It was contextualized to fit the educational realities of the target population. The instrument consists of a Likert scale with 30 items, distributed across the four dimensions, as detailed in Table 2.

To evaluate teaching performance, a supervision and monitoring form developed by the Ministry of Education [22] was applied. This instrument assesses two key dimensions: preparation for teaching and teaching for student learning. The structure and indicators of the form are detailed in Table 3.

Table 1. Structure of the test to measure EI

Variable	Dimensions	Indicators	Items	Rating
EI	Personal skills	Self-awareness	1-10	5=very high
		Self-regulation	11-23	4=high
		Motivation	24-30	3=regular
	Social skills	Empathy	31-42	2=low
		Social skills	43-50	1=very low

Table 2. Structure of the test to measure IC

Variable	Dimensions	Indicators	Items	Rating	
IC	Communication	Communication/information sharing	1-2	5=very high	
		Speed/agility	3-4	4=high	
		Respect	5	3=regular	
		Acceptance	6	2=low	
		Spaces and schedules	7	1=very low	
		Concealing information	8		
		Motivation	Satisfaction	9-10	
			Recognition	11	
	Prestige		12		
	Trust	Autonomy	13		
		Trust	14-16		
	Participation	Sincerity	17-18		
		Teachers foster participation	19-23		
		Teams and work meetings	24-26		
		Formal and informal groups	27-29		
	Coordination	30			

Table 3. Supervision and monitoring form to measure teaching performance in the classroom

Variable	Dimensions	Indicators	Items	Rating
Teaching performance in the classroom	Preparation for teaching and learning	Long and short-term planning	1-3	1=unsatisfactory
		Setting learning objectives	4-6	2=in progress
		Daily planning components	7-9	3=satisfactory
		Evaluation of planning outcomes	10-12	4=outstanding
	Teaching for student learning	Actively involves students in learning	1	1=unsatisfactory
		Promotes reasoning, creativity, critical thinking	2	2=in progress
		Evaluates learning progress for feedback	3	3=satisfactory
		Fosters respect and closeness	4	4=outstanding
		Positively regulates student behavior	5	

2.4.1. Data collection procedure

This study employed a rigorous data collection process to ensure validity, reliability, and confidentiality. Teachers participated voluntarily and anonymously, completing questionnaires in a controlled setting. The data were then digitized, coded into a database, and analyzed using statistical tools, including Pearson's correlation coefficient, scatter plots, and descriptive statistics to evaluate and interpret the relationships between variables.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Descriptive analysis: for the emotional intelligence variable

As shown in Table 4, the results indicate that most teachers demonstrate high or regular levels of EI across all five dimensions: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Self-awareness (53.8%) and self-regulation (59.3%) show the highest proportions at a high level, reflecting strong emotional management. However, motivation is primarily rated as regular (52.4%), suggesting a need for improvement. In terms of social aptitudes, empathy (44.8%) and social skills (46.8%) are mostly high, yet 5.5% of teachers scored low in empathy, emphasizing the importance of targeted strategies to enhance this critical competence in the educational setting.

Table 4. Results by dimensions and subdimensions of EI

Rating	Dimensions									
	Personal aptitudes					Social aptitudes				
	Self-awareness		Self-regulation		Motivation		Empathy		Social skills	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Very high	12	8.3	10	6.8	26	17.9	10	6.8	7	4.8
High	78	53.8	86	59.3	38	26.2	65	44.8	68	46.8
Regular	48	33.1	45	31.1	76	52.4	62	42.7	64	44.2
Low	7	4.8	4	2.7	5	3.4	8	5.5	6	4.1
Total	145	100.0	145	100.0	145	100.0	145	100	145	100

Figure 1 shows that most participants have a high level of EI across all subdimensions. Motivation has the highest proportion in very high but also shows variability with many ratings in regular. Empathy and social skills are mostly rated as regular, indicating a need for improvement in interpersonal connections. Self-awareness and self-regulation are strong in high, though some individuals scored low, suggesting the need for additional support. These findings emphasize the importance of targeted training programs to enhance emotional competencies, especially in interpersonal interactions and emotional regulation.

Figure 1. Results by dimensions and subdimensions of EI

3.2. Descriptive analysis: for teaching performance in the classroom variable

As shown in Table 5, the results indicate that most teachers demonstrate satisfactory or outstanding performance in both preparation for teaching and learning and teaching for student learning, with 52.4% and 64.8% rated as satisfactory, respectively. Only a small percentage were classified as “in progress” (5.5% in preparation and 10.3% in teaching), highlighting specific areas for improvement. Unsatisfactory ratings were minimal (2.0% in preparation and 4.2% in teaching), suggesting that the majority of teachers meet the expected standards. Overall, the findings reflect a positive trend in teaching performance, though there remains a need to strengthen instructional strategies to enhance teaching effectiveness.

Figure 2 compares preparation for teaching and teaching for student learning across four performance categories. Preparation has a higher percentage of outstanding ratings (40% vs. 20.6%), while teaching is more frequently rated as satisfactory (64.8% vs. 52.4%) and has more evaluations in lower categories. This suggests that teachers are well-prepared theoretically but face challenges in applying effective teaching strategies. To bridge this gap, practical training and continuous feedback should be prioritized to improve classroom execution and increase outstanding teaching performance.

Table 5. Results by dimensions of teaching performance in the classroom

Rating	Dimensions			
	Preparation for teaching and learning		Teaching for student learning	
	F	%	F	%
Outstanding	58	40.0	30	20.6
Satisfactory	76	52.4	94	64.8
In progress	8	5.5	15	10.3
Unsatisfactory	3	2.0	6	4.2
Total	145	100.0	145	100.0

Figure 2. Results by dimensions of teaching performance in the classroom

3.3. Institutional climate variable

The results in Table 6 show that the four evaluated dimensions present significant challenges, with a predominance of ratings in the regular category (between 44.1% and 57.9%) and significant proportions in lower categories (poor and very poor), especially in communication (24.1%) and trust (22%). Although motivation and participation have higher proportions in higher categories (very good and good, with 33% and 22.7%, respectively), areas for improvement are also evident. These results indicate the need for strategies focused on strengthening communication, fostering trust-based relationships, increasing both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and promoting more active and meaningful participation in the evaluated processes.

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of IC ratings across four dimensions: communication, motivation, confidence, and participation. The regular category predominates, especially in participation (57.9%) and confidence (54.4%), indicating average perceptions. Motivation has the highest proportion of positive ratings (33% in very good/good), while communication and confidence show more negative ratings (24.1% and 22% in bad/very bad, respectively), highlighting key areas for improvement. Overall, while motivation is relatively strong, communication and confidence require attention to enhance IC perceptions.

Table 6. Results by dimensions of IC

Rating	Dimensions							
	Communication		Motivation		Trust		Participation	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
Very good	4	2.7	8	5.5	4	2.7	7	4.8
Good	28	19.3	40	27.5	30	20.7	26	17.9
Regular	78	53.7	64	44.1	79	54.4	84	57.9
Poor	34	23.4	29	20.0	28	19.3	24	16.5
Very poor	1	0.7	4	2.7	4	2.7	4	2.7
Total	145	100.0	145	100.0	145	100.0	145	100

Figure 3. IC level results

3.4. Correlation analysis

The correlation analysis was conducted using the Pearson correlation matrix, a statistical tool that measures the strength and direction of the linear relationship between pairs of variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) ranges from -1 to +1, where +1 indicates a perfect positive relationship, -1 indicates a perfect negative relationship, and 0 indicates no linear relationship. In our study, the matrix was used to assess the relationships between EI, teaching performance, and IC, providing insights into how strongly and in what direction each pair of variables is related. This approach allowed us to identify significant correlations, such as the positive association between EI and teaching performance, helping to draw conclusions about how these factors interact in the educational context. Table 7 shows the correlation matrix illustrating the relationship between all the mentioned dimensions.

Table 7. Pearson correlation matrix

Dimension	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. Self-awareness	1.000	0.996	0.683	0.957	0.958	0.603	0.844	0.490	0.704	0.536	0.493
2. Self-regulation	0.996	1.000	0.621	0.929	0.932	0.635	0.878	0.418	0.644	0.465	0.419
3. Motivation	0.683	0.621	1.000	0.847	0.836	0.189	0.284	0.811	0.846	0.852	0.881
4. Empathy	0.957	0.929	0.847	1.000	0.999	0.409	0.659	0.703	0.858	0.748	0.721
5. Social skills	0.958	0.932	0.836	0.999	1.000	0.396	0.657	0.696	0.853	0.743	0.715
6. Teaching preparation	0.603	0.635	0.189	0.409	0.396	1.000	0.894	-0.255	-0.029	-0.225	-0.236
7. Learning facilitation	0.844	0.878	0.284	0.659	0.657	0.894	1.000	-0.017	0.249	0.019	-0.030
8. Communication	0.490	0.418	0.811	0.703	0.696	-0.255	-0.017	1.000	0.963	0.993	0.981
9. Dimensional motivation	0.704	0.644	0.846	0.858	0.853	-0.029	0.249	0.963	1.000	0.968	0.940
10. Confidence	0.536	0.465	0.852	0.748	0.743	-0.225	0.019	0.993	0.968	1.000	0.993
11. Participation	0.493	0.419	0.881	0.721	0.715	-0.236	-0.030	0.981	0.940	0.993	1.000

3.4.1. Strong positive relationships

The results reveal strong correlations among key variables. Notably, empathy and social skills (r=0.999) show that greater empathy enhances interpersonal abilities. Similarly, confidence and participation (r=0.993) and communication and motivation (r=0.962) highlight the importance of emotional and communicative factors in promoting active engagement and motivation in the educational context.

3.4.2. Moderate relationships

The results reveal strong correlations between key emotional and motivational factors. Self-awareness and empathy (0.957) indicate that greater self-awareness enhances empathy. Motivation and empathy (0.847) suggest that motivated individuals tend to be more empathetic. Additionally, motivation and participation (0.881) highlight that higher motivation is linked to increased engagement and involvement.

3.4.3. Weak or negative relationships

The results indicate weak negative correlations between preparation for teaching and communication (-0.255), as well as participation (-0.236). This suggests that stronger instructional planning does not automatically improve interpersonal or collaborative skills. Therefore, it is essential to promote integrated training that combines pedagogical preparation with communication and participation competencies.

The heat map in Figure 4 visually represents the Pearson correlation coefficients between the different dimensions evaluated. The heat map uses a color scale to represent the strength and direction of correlations: dark red indicates strong positive relationships (+1), dark blue represents strong negative relationships (-1), and light colors or white reflect weak or no correlation (values near 0), serving as a visual aid for interpreting variable associations. The analysis highlights strong positive correlations such as between empathy and social skills (0.999), confidence and participation (0.993), and communication and motivation (0.963), underscoring the interplay between emotional and interpersonal competencies. Moderate correlations were observed between motivation and empathy (0.847) and motivation and participation (0.881), suggesting that motivated individuals tend to be more empathetic and engaged. In contrast, weak negative correlations were found between preparation for teaching and communication (-0.255), and between preparation for teaching and participation (-0.236), indicating that strong instructional planning may not necessarily enhance communication or collaborative skills. Overall, the heat map reveals a clear trend: while personal and emotional abilities are strongly interrelated, technical aspects such as teaching preparation show weaker alignment with interpersonal dimensions, emphasizing the need for more integrated teacher development strategies.

Figure 4. Heat map of correlations between the dimensions

3.5. Proposed emotional intelligence intervention program for secondary school teachers

The program titled strengthening emotional competencies for improved teacher performance and IC aims to develop EI in secondary school teachers to enhance their classroom effectiveness and foster a positive institutional environment. It consists of three phases: an initial diagnosis to assess teachers’

Emotional intelligence in teaching: a key to performance and institutional ... (Benjamin Maraza-Quispe)

emotional competencies and perceptions of SC using standardized tools; a training phase comprising four modules focused on self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy and social skills, and motivation and resilience; and a final phase of applied practice and evaluation through a 12-week intervention with weekly 3-hour sessions. Program success is measured by a 15% improvement in EI scores, better teaching performance evaluations, and positive IC feedback.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reinforce the growing body of evidence that highlights EI as a fundamental factor in improving teaching performance and IC. The positive correlation observed between EI and these two dimensions suggests that enhancing teachers' emotional competencies contributes not only to instructional effectiveness but also to the creation of a more collaborative, trusting, and motivating school environment. This aligns with Ghrayeb [23] expanded model of EI, which identifies 12 key competencies grouped under self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management dimensions essential for high-performance teaching.

Teaching performance, understood as the combination of pedagogical competence, classroom management, and the ability to foster student motivation [7], has been shown to improve when teachers exhibit high levels of EI. As noted by Goleman [8], emotionally intelligent teachers can better handle interpersonal conflicts, manage classroom dynamics, and maintain student engagement. Similarly, the notion of IC, as a set of shared perceptions regarding communication, trust, and support in the work environment [9], has been strongly associated with teacher satisfaction and performance. Study by Luqman *et al.* [24] confirm that a positive organizational climate significantly enhances job performance, particularly in educational environments where interaction and trust are key elements.

Several studies have explored the interrelationship between these variables. For instance, study by Brasseur *et al.* [13] developed and validated the PEC, a robust instrument that assesses five core emotional competencies. This tool demonstrated strong psychometric properties and proved useful in evaluating the impact of emotional skills on work performance and well-being, providing a methodological foundation relevant to our research. In a different context, Amin *et al.* [14] examined EI levels in higher education faculty in India, revealing gender-based differences and underscoring the importance of inclusive teacher training programs. Moreover, Akhtar and Mali [15] explored the connection between spiritual intelligence and work engagement, finding that emotional and spiritual competencies jointly influence professional performance, particularly when considering gender and urban-rural contexts. These findings resonate with study by Kumar and Anshika [16], who showed that EI is not strongly determined by socioeconomic or cultural factors, reinforcing the idea that emotional skills can be developed through intentional training in any educational setting.

From a leadership perspective, study by Al Shehhi *et al.* [17] found that low EI among school principals negatively affects SC and leadership effectiveness. This supports our argument for integrating EI development not only in teacher preparation but also in educational leadership programs. Iram research [18], which demonstrated how various components of EI influence different aspects of the institutional environment, further validates our findings. Additionally, Go *et al.* [19] emphasized that the ability to compartmentalize personal challenges, closely tied to EI, is key to sustaining consistent and effective teaching practices. Further support for this relationship comes from the study by Mukhtar and Fook [25], who found that leadership styles and EI significantly influence teachers' attitudes toward organizational change, suggesting that emotionally intelligent educators are more adaptable and resilient in dynamic institutional contexts. Similarly, Nagalingam *et al.* [26] highlighted the mediating role of work engagement in the link between EI and organizational commitment, reinforcing the idea that EI not only benefits individual performance but also strengthens institutional cohesion and long-term teacher involvement.

The evidence gathered across various studies consistently supports the positive influence of EI in educational and organizational contexts. Study by Paredes-Saavedra *et al.* [27] demonstrate a strong correlation between EI, teaching performance, and IC in basic education, while Banga [28] highlight the interaction between EI and self-confidence as key to effective teaching and student engagement. Similarly, Kostyuk and Didyk [29] emphasize the role of EI in improving teaching methods and classroom management, recommending the recruitment and training of emotionally competent teachers. Lastly, Kamel *et al.* [30] present findings from the healthcare field, showing that EI is significantly associated with perceptions of patient safety climate—an insight that can be extrapolated to education, where a positive emotional environment enhances both well-being and performance. Collectively, these studies align with our research by underscoring that strengthening teachers' emotional competencies not only improves their individual performance but also enhances the IC and overall educational outcomes.

5. CONCLUSION

There is a direct and significant correlation between EI, teacher performance, and IC, underscoring the importance of these variables in enhancing the educational environment. Teachers' EI not only affects their classroom performance but also contributes to strengthening a positive IC, fostering more effective interactions among members of the educational community. A favorable IC enhances teacher performance and contributes to better organizational dynamics, influencing the quality of education provided. The research reinforces the idea that EI, teacher professional competence (TPC), and IC are interconnected and that their enhancement through training programs and organizational strategies can significantly improve educational quality and workplace well-being in schools. The results support the need to design and implement EI training programs for teachers to optimize their performance and improve the IC.

This study provides empirical evidence that can guide decision-making in educational management, highlighting the relevance of considering emotional competencies as a key component for teachers' professional development and institutional well-being. Future research should explore the long-term effects of EI training on teaching performance and IC. Additionally, studies could examine gender differences, cultural influences, and the impact of specific interventions. Expanding research to different educational levels and incorporating qualitative methods would provide deeper insights into EI development.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : **O**riting - **O**riginal Draft

E : **E**riting - **R**eview & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest affecting this research.

INFORMED CONSENT

All participants in this study provided informed consent prior to their participation, ensuring their understanding and acceptance of the study's objectives, procedures, and potential implications.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The research related to human use has been complied with all the relevant national regulations and institutional policies in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration and has been approved by the authors' institutional review board or equivalent committee.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study will be available in OSFHOME https://osf.io/ebxv4/?view_only=0fb4624f25b7464aae71366b422ff122.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Filice and W. J. Weese, "Developing Emotional Intelligence," *Encyclopedia*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 583–599, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.3390/encyclopedia4010037.
- [2] J. C. Meniado, "Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Emotional Intelligence of EFL Teachers in Saudi Arabia: Implications to Teaching Performance and Institutional Effectiveness," *Arab World English Journal*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 3–14, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.24093/awej/vol11no4.1.
- [3] M. K. Bighami, H. K. Soltani, M. Panah, and F. Abdi, "Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Testing the Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction)," *Psychological Reports*, vol. 110, no. 3, pp. 899–914, 2012.
- [4] M. A. Brackett, S. E. Rivers, S. Shiffman, N. Lerner, and P. Salovey, "Relating emotional abilities to social functioning: A comparison of self-report and performance measures of emotional intelligence.," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol. 91, no. 4, pp. 780–795, Oct. 2006, doi: 10.1037/0022-3514.91.4.780.
- [5] E. G. Fernández-Abascal and M. D. Martín-Díaz, "Dimensions of emotional intelligence related to physical and mental health and to health behaviors," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 6, p. 317, 2015, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2015.00317.
- [6] M. Fadli, B. Modding, Mapparenta, Ramlawati, and J. Zakari, "The Influence of Work Motivation, Emotional Intelligence, and Competence on Occupation Satisfaction Through Work Achievement in the Library Service in South Sulawesi," *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, vol. 8, no. 6, p. e02306, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i6.2306.
- [7] A. K. Vesely, D. H. Saklofske, and A. D. W. Leschied, "Teachers—The Vital Resource," *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 71–89, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1177/0829573512468855.
- [8] D. Goleman, *Emotional intelligence: Why it is more important than IQ*. Barcelona: Editorial Kairós (in Spanish), 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://iuymca.edu.ar/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/La-Inteligencia-Emocional-Daniel-Goleman-1.pdf>
- [9] D. W. Organ, "Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Recent Trends and Developments," *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 295–306, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032117-104536.
- [10] A. Somech and I. Oplatka, *Organizational citizenship behavior in schools: examining the impact and opportunities within educational systems*. London: Routledge, 2015.
- [11] R. M. M. González and N. A. Ibarra, "Emotional intelligence in education," (in Spanish), *Revista Complutense de Educación*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 887–888, Jan. 1970, doi: 10.5209/rev_RCED.2016.v27.n2.52196.
- [12] E. Yaakobi and J. Weisberg, "Organizational Citizenship Behavior Predicts Quality, Creativity, and Efficiency Performance: The Roles of Occupational and Collective Efficacies," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 11, p. 758, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00758.
- [13] S. Brasseur, J. Grégoire, R. Bourdu, and M. Mikolajczak, "The Profile of Emotional Competence (PEC): Development and Validation of a Self-Reported Measure that Fits Dimensions of Emotional Competence Theory," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. e62635, May 2013, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0062635.
- [14] S. Amin, Nisha, and K. Chaudhary, "Emotional Intelligence of Teachers Working in Higher Education Institutions in Haryana in Relation to Gender and Types of School," *European Economic Letters (EEL)*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1412–1417, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.52783/eel.v14i1.1196.
- [15] P. Akhtar and A. Mali, "The spectrum of spiritual intelligence among the college teachers: a study of gender, locality and level of job involvement of Jammu Division," *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 6–19, 2019. [Online]. Available: https://ijcrt.org/viewfull.php?&p_id=IJCRT1134165
- [16] D. Kumar and Anshika, "Comparative study of emotional intelligence of reserved category and unreserved category students at higher secondary level," *Knowledgeable Research: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, vol. 2, no. 12, pp. 20–27, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.57067/rxwckp17.
- [17] M. Al Shehhi, K. Alzouebi, and A. Ankit, "An examination of the emotional intelligence of school principals and the impact on school climate in public schools in the United Arab Emirates," *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1269–1289, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1108/JARHE-09-2020-0287.
- [18] N. Iram, "Effect of Teachers' Emotional Intelligence on School Climate at Secondary School Level," *Bulletin of Education and Research*, vol. 44, no. 3, pp. 18–36, 2022.
- [19] M. B. Go, R. A. Golbin, S. P. Velos, and G. P. Bate, "Filipino Teachers' Compartmentalization Ability, Emotional Intelligence, and Teaching Performance," *Asian Journal of University Education*, vol. 16, no. 3, p. 27, 2020, doi: 10.24191/ajue.v16i3.7912.
- [20] J. V. Boybanting and R. C. Tantiado, "Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Performance of Teachers," *International Journal of Research Publications*, vol. 129, no. 1, pp. 392–403, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.47119/IJRP1001291720235288.
- [21] M. M. Bris, "Working environment and learning organizations," (in Spanish), *Educar*, vol. 27, pp. 103–117, Jul. 2000, doi: 10.5565/rev/educar.251.
- [22] Ministerio de Educación del Perú (MINEDU), *Good Teaching Performance Framework*. Lima: MINEDU (in Spanish), 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://bit.ly/4fpkCeZ>
- [23] F. Ghayeb *et al.*, "Exploring the relationship between emotional intelligence and communication skills in nurses: a cross-sectional study," *BMC Nursing*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 1002, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.1186/s12912-025-03679-5.
- [24] M. S. Luqman, J. U. Rehman, Z. U. Islam, and S. D. Khan, "Effect of organizational climate upon the job performance of instructors' physical education," *Pedagogy of Physical Culture and Sports*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 72–76, 2020, doi: 10.15561/26649837.2020.0204.

- [25] N. A. Mukhtar and C. Y. Fook, "The Effects of Perceived Leadership Styles and Emotional Intelligence on Attitude toward Organizational Change among Secondary School Teachers," *Asian Journal of University Education*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 36–45, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.24191/ajue.v16i2.10295.
- [26] U. D. Nagalingam, N. B. yah A. Kadir, and S. M. Hoesni, "The mediating role of work engagement in the relationship between emotional intelligence and organisational commitment among higher education institution lecturers," *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 31–53, 2019, doi: 10.26803/ijlter.18.8.3.
- [27] M. Paredes-Saavedra, M. Vallejos, S. Huanchuire-Vega, W. Morales-García, and L. Geraldo-Campos, "Work Team Effectiveness: Importance of Organizational Culture, Work Climate, Leadership, Creative Synergy, and Emotional Intelligence in University Employees," *Administrative Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 11, p. 280, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.3390/admsci14110280.
- [28] B. Banga, "Exploring the Interplay Between Self-Confidence and Emotional Intelligence in College-Level Educators: Implications for Teaching Effectiveness and Student Engagement," *International Journal for Multidimensional Research Perspectives*, vol. 2, no. 11, pp. 16–37, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.61877/ijmrp.v2i11.211.
- [29] O. Kostyuk and L. Didyk, "The necessity of fostering emotional intelligence in teaching a foreign language to university students in the context of online learning," *Naukovi zapiski Nacional'nogo universitetu «Ostroz'ka akademiâ». Seriâ «Filologîâ»*, vol. 14, no. 82, pp. 116–121, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.25264/2519-2558-2022-14(82)-116-121.
- [30] A. E. Kamel, A. M. Seada, and S. H. Aly, "Relationship between nurses' emotional intelligence and their perception of patient safety climate," *Egyptian Nursing Journal*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 327–336, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.4103/enj.enj_22_22.

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